

Social Work Professionals in Healthcare: An Exploratory Study of Staff Knowledge and Attitudes in Obio/Akpor LGA, Rivers State

Mina Margaret Ogbanga

Rivers State University

Mina.Ogbanga@ust.edu.ng

Abstract

This paper is on staff knowledge on the roles of social works professionals in medical field; a case study of government teaching hospitals in Obia/Akpor local government area, Rivers State. The study was conducted at University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital (UPTH) Port Harcourt. The area is selected as one of the government hospitals with social work professionals working with other medical field practitioners. The data were collected using questionnaires which were given to respondents and the analysis of the collected data portrayed the factors that challenge integration of social work professionals in medical services. The study which is dominantly quantitative in nature, adopts the structured questionnaire in the generation of primary data for the study. The result indicates that most the medical staffs are not aware of the role of social workers at the hospital. This is true since the mean values are below the benchmark of 2.5, meaning that most of the respondents were on the disagree range of the scale, but item one which has the highest mean score shows an indication that the staffs are aware that social workers are part of the medical team but do not know the roles they play in the well-being of patients in the hospital. Thus it is clear that medical staffs are not aware that social workers supports patients financially, provide psycho-social therapy to patients, and also acts as a mediator between the patient and staff hence, their services are underutilized in the hospital. The paper recommended among others that the Government should employ more hospital social workers so that they can be able to meet the demand of their services to patients and clients at the hospital.

Introduction

Medical social work is a sub-discipline of social work, also known as hospital social work. Medical social workers typically work in a hospital, outpatient clinic, community health agency, skilled nursing facility, long-term care facility or hospice. They work with patients and their families in need of psychosocial help. Medical social workers assess the psychosocial functioning of patients and families and intervene as necessary. Social workers address questions such as: Who should we intervene and when should they intervene?(Wodarski, 2012)Interventions may include connecting patients and families to necessary resources and supports in the community like preventative care; providing psychotherapy, supportive counseling, or grief counseling; or helping a patient to expand and strengthen their network of social supports. Role of a medical social worker is to "restore

balance in an individual's personal, family and social life, in order to help that person maintain or recover his/her health and strengthen his/her ability to adapt and reintegrate into society" (Ordreprofessionnel des travailleurs sociaux du Québec, OPTSQ, 1999). Professionals in this field typically work with other disciplines such as medicine, nursing, physical, occupational, speech and recreational therapy. Medical workers who work in the pediatric Aerodigestive Program are imperative to assist the families to control the specific necessities of their child, while striving to escalate coping and the wellbeing of their patients. (Fonash, 2018)

Research Aim and Objectives

Examine the staff knowledge on the roles of social works professionals in medical field.

Research Questions

What is the level of the staff knowledge on the roles of social works professionals in medical field?

Scope of the Study

For the sake of time and limited resources this paper seeks to investigate the challenges facing integration of social work professionals into medical institutions in Obio-Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State. The study will primarily focus on the health care delivery of medical social welfare department of University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital (UPTH), as this is part of the Government Teaching Hospital in Obio-Akpor LGA with a functional social work department. Also, the researcher seeks to understand the level of awareness of social work services among health workers.

Significance of the Study

This study seeks to add to the existing knowledge in social work literature, therefore, this study will be of ultimate importance to students seeking to develop their knowledge in the discipline and all social workers in any specialty, including; family social work, medical social work, social work with the elderly, social work with people in crisis, social work intervention with the vulnerable population.

It is also the aim of the researcher to influence government policy through this research paper, therefore this study serves as an eye opener to the happenings in the society some are known while others are unknown by the government officers.

Limitations

The research only focused on Government Teaching Hospitals in Obia/Akpor LGA in Rivers State. Hence, the findings may not be adequate in generalizing it to cover other medical institutions. The second factor is that there is a wide geographical scope of Hospitals in Rivers State which was difficult to visit all which may affect conclusion and generalization of findings. Another major limitation is that the respondents of this study are medical workers

who have little or no time for activities outside their working schedule. Hence, the retrieval of questionnaire was greatly as only 215 out of 267 questionnaires that were distributed were retrieved.

Definition of Terms

Client

Client refers to the “individual, group, family, or community that seeks or is provided with professional services” (Barker, 2013, p. 73). For purposes of these standards, the term “client” refers to an individual. The term “patient” is more commonly used by social workers employed in health care settings.

Biopsychosocial–Spiritual Perspective

A biopsychosocial–spiritual perspective recognizes the importance of whole person care and takes into account a client’s physical or medical condition; emotional or psychological state; socioeconomic, sociocultural, and sociopolitical status; and spiritual needs and concerns.

Bioethics

Bioethics is “the analysis and study of legal, moral, social, and ethical considerations involving the biological and medical sciences” (Barker, 2013).

Case Management

Case management is a collaborative process to plan, seek, advocate for, and monitor services, resources, and supports on behalf of a client. Case management enables a health care social worker to serve clients who may require the services of various health care providers and facilities, community-based organizations, social services agencies, and other programs.

Research Aim and Objectives

- (i) Identify staff awareness on the presence of social work professionals in the hospital

Research Questions

- (i) What is the level of staff awareness on the presence of social work professionals in the hospital?

Scope of the Study

For the sake of time and limited resources this paper seeks to investigate the challenges facing integration of social work professionals into medical institutions in Obio-Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State. The study will primarily focus on the health care delivery of medical social welfare department of University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital (UPTH), as this is part of the Government Teaching Hospital in Obio-Akpor LGA with a

functional social work department. Also, the researcher seeks to understand the level of awareness of social work services among health workers.

Significance of the Study

The study aimed at identifying challenges facing integration of social work professionals into medical cadre. The identified challenges shall be communicated to the Ministry of Social Welfare and Rehabilitation Centre and the heads of department to make them understand the existing challenges facing integration of social work professionals into medical practice. The results of this research study can help in developing strategies on how to eliminate those challenges hence maximize the benefits to clients who require social workers interventions. This study will assist to create awareness to the local government authority on the need to strengthen the social welfare department in terms of allocating adequate funds as well as increasing the number of social workers into medical practice. Moreover, on job programs might be designed to orient all staff on the roles and functions of social workers into medical practice including cases required to be attended by social workers.

Limitations

The research only focused on Government Teaching Hospitals in Obia/Akpor LGA in Rivers State. Hence, the findings may not be adequate in generalizing it to cover other medical institutions. The second factor is that there is a wide geographical scope of Hospitals in Rivers State which was difficult to visit all which may affect conclusion and generalization of findings.

Another major limitation is that the respondent of this study are medical workers who have little or no time for activities outside their working schedule. Hence, the retrieval of questionnaire was greatly as only 215 out of 267 questionnaires that were distributed were retrieved.

Definition of Terms

Social Worker

Within the United States, a social worker is an individual who possesses a baccalaureate or master's degree in social work from a school or program accredited by the Council on Social Work Education. Although all 50 states and the District of Columbia license or certify social workers, licensure and certification laws vary by state. Each social worker should be licensed or certified, as applicable and required, at the level appropriate to her or his scope of practice in the practitioner's jurisdiction(s).

Meaning and definition of social work

“Social work is a profession concerned with helping individuals, families, groups and communities to enhance their individual and collective well-being. It aims to help people develop their skills and their ability to use their own resources and those of the community to resolve problems. Social work is concerned with individual and personal problems but also with broader social issues such as poverty, unemployment, and domestic violence.” – Canadian Association of Social Workers (CASW2008).

Theoretical Literature Review

Systems Theory

The most famous theory drawing on a pluralist frame of reference is Dunlop's (1958) systems theory, which argues that industrial relations are best regarded as a subsystem of the wider social system. The theory holds work to be governed by a wide range of formal and informal rules and regulations, which cover everything from recruitment, holidays, performance, wages, hours, and a myriad of other details of employment. It asserts that these rules are what industrial actors try to determine, that their establishment is influenced by the wider environmental context in which the actors operate, and that the actors themselves share an interest in maintaining the processes of negotiation and conflict resolution. On the back of these assertions, four elements are held to make up the system of industrial relations rule-making. The first is industrial actors, which consists of employers and their representatives (i.e. employer associations), employees and their representatives (i.e., trade unions), and external agencies with an interest in industrial relations (i.e., government departments and labour courts). The second is the environmental context, which was made up of prevailing economic and technological conditions, as well as the distribution of power in wider society, each of which is thought to influence or constrain the actions of actors engaged in industrial relations. The third is the so called 'web of rules' that governs the employment relationship and is held to be the outcome of interactions between the actors. The last is a 'binding ideology', which is a set of common beliefs and understandings that serve to encourage compromises on the part of each actor for the sake of making the system operable. An important aspect of this framework conceives the industrial relations system as self-adjusting towards equilibrium. In so far as change in one element had repercussions for the other elements, they are held to set in motion a range of processes that invariably restores a sense of order on the system.

Human Relations Theory

The second theory comes from the so-called human relations school (see: Maslow, 1954; Mayo, 1933; Child, 1967). In this case the reduction of organizational tension is held to rest on the ability of individuals to achieve self-fulfillment in the workplace. Workers are regarded as qualitatively different to other resources used in production. Thus, if workers are denied autonomy on the job, or are reduced to acting as mere extensions of the machinery they operate, or are given work that inhibits their capacity to create and think, it is argued that they will invariably find ways to subvert the methods of control that enforce these conditions.

The principal task of management on this conception is to manipulate workplace relations in ways that enable employees to feel personal satisfaction with being involved with the organization. To this end, companies operating on this basis are expected to recognize the right of employees to have a say in how they are governed. They are also expected to take an active interest in developing the skills of employees as a means of demonstrating a commitment to their personal well-being. In whatever form, the aim of this managerial approach to employee relations is one that seeks to reduce internal tensions by developing the sense of workplace satisfaction felt by employees through techniques that involve them in the organization and regulation of work.

Brief History of Social work

The practice and profession of social work has a relatively modern and scientific origin, and is generally considered to have developed out of three strands (Huff .D1900). The first was individual casework, a strategy pioneered by the Charity Organization Society in the mid-19th century, which was founded by Helen Bosanquet and Octavia Hill in London, England. Most historians identify COS as the pioneering organization of the social theory that led to the emergence of social work as a professional occupation. (Lymbery 2005).COS had its main focus on individual casework. The second was social administration, which included various forms of poverty relief – 'relief of paupers'. Statewide poverty relief could be said to have its roots in the English Poor Laws of the 17th century, but was first systematized through the efforts of the Charity Organization Society. The third consisted of social action – rather than engaging in the resolution of immediate individual requirements, the emphasis was placed on political action working through the community and the group to improve their social conditions and thereby alleviate poverty. This approach was developed originally by the Settlement House Movement (Lymbery 2005). This was accompanied by a less easily defined movement; the development of institutions to deal with the entire range of social problems. All had their most rapid growth during the nineteenth century, and laid the foundation basis for modern social work, both in theory and in practice (Allyn& Bacon, 2011). Professional social work originated in 19th century England, and had its roots in the social and economic upheaval wrought by the Industrial Revolution, in particular the societal struggle to deal with the resultant mass urban-based poverty and its related problems. Because poverty was the main focus of early social work, it was intricately linked with the idea of charity work (Allyn& Bacon, 2011). Other important historical figures that shaped the growth of the social work profession are Jane Addams, who founded the Hull House in Chicago and won the Nobel Peace Prize in 1931; Mary Ellen Richmond, who wrote *Social Diagnosis*, one of the first social work books to incorporate law, medicine, psychiatry, psychology, and history; and William Beveridge, who created the social welfare state, framing the debate on social work within the context of social welfare provision

Major Issues and Constraints on Social Work: An African Perspective

Compared to other helping professions like medicine, psychiatry and nursing, social work is a relatively young profession. In Europe and North America, social work emerged in the late nineteenth and early twentieth century. In Africa social work is even younger, essentially a product of European colonialism. Despite its recent development, social work is a rapidly growing field. The profession's phenomenal growth and development throughout the world is a clear indication of its contribution to the alleviation of social problems. However, social work is still a fledgling and struggling profession, whose theory and practice are shrouded in mystery and controversy. Indeed, a number of scholars have described social work as a profession of many faces: stimulating, challenging, confusing and even frustrating. The enigma and controversy surrounding social work is partly rooted in its newness and also in the wide array of the concepts, theories, principles, methods and techniques which social workers use. Accordingly, the major issues and problems facing social work today revolve around its structure, functions, identity, resources and education. (Midgley, 2007; Macpherson & Midgley, 2008). Romile and Radithokwa (2006) in a journal article, said; a major problem which social workers have to deal with is the vagueness and controversy surrounding the meaning, objectives, functions and methods of their profession. Social work as a field of study and practice is not well understood, especially in Africa. This is largely due to the fact that social work is a profession still in its infancy. Below an attempt is made to define and explain the characteristics, origins and functions of social work.

Research Method

The Study Area

The study was conducted at University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital (UPTH) Port Harcourt. The area is selected as one of the government hospitals with social work professionals working with other medical field practitioners.

Research Design

Nachimias (2003) defined research design as "the blue print that enables the investigators to come up with solutions to problems and guide him/her in the various stages of the research. This study adopts a descriptive cross sectional survey. Cross-sectional surveys are studies aimed at determining the frequency or level of a particular attribute in a defined population at a particular point in time. A cross sectional study is commonly used in medical and social science researches. A cross sectional study or prevalence study is the type of observational study that involves the analysis of data collected from a population or representative subset at one specific point in time. The data were collected using questionnaires which were given to respondents and the analysis of the collected data portrayed the factors that challenge integration of social work professionals in medical services.

Population of the Study

According to Nachimias (2003) population is defined as “the aggregate of all cases that conform to some designated set of specification. Kombo and Tromp (2006) defined population as the largest group from which the sample is taken. The population of the study comprises all the medical staffs of the University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital working with social welfare department in the hospital which is about 800 in number. This number was obtained from the human resource department of the hospital.

Sampling Techniques and Sample Size

Nachimias (2003) defined sample as “the sub set of a population”. Thus, in view of the fact that our study involves a finite population, a sample size that can be possibly reached is obtained. Kothari (2004) defined sampling techniques or procedure as “a definite plan for obtaining a sample for population given. The study sample size was arrived at using the Taro Yamen’s 1970 formula.

The sample size was calculated by using the Taro Yamen Sample size determination formula;

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Whereby; n=Sample size, N= total population (800) and e= an acceptable error (0.05).

$$\text{Therefore } n = \frac{800}{1+800(0.05)^2} = 266.7$$

In this research study the sample size was 267.

Data Collection Method

Questionnaire

The questionnaire involves a set of questions to collect information from subjects on their perceptions, feelings to the subject under study. It helps in providing accurate data that are quantifiable easily. The study which is dominantly quantitative in nature, adopts the structured questionnaire in the generation of primary data for the study. Copies of questionnaire would be personally administered, followed up and retrieved.

Data Analysis Approach

Braun and Clarke (2006) state that “thematic analysis is a qualitative analytic method for identifying, analyzing and reporting patterns within data. Thematic analysis minimally organizes and described data set in details. However, it goes further than this and interprets various aspect of the research topic. Data collected from the field were structured to ensure

consistency of responses. Data generated were arranged and coded according to themes and then fed into the data editor section of Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS 21.0). Analysis were undertaken in two phases beginning with the demographic profile, using percentages, describes the frequencies of responses to various sample characteristics. Secondly the research questions and findings were analyzed through mean scores and standard deviations

Validity of the Instrument

According to Babbie (2007), the term validity refers to the extent to which an empirical measure adequately reflects the real meaning of the concept under consideration. Validity is defined as the ability of the scale to measure what it is designed or purported to measure. For validity of the measurement to be established, there should be a complete absence of measurement error. It is important that a reliability and validity test be carried out comprehensively at every stage of the research work. Babbie (2007) posit that, after operationalizing, defining variables and applying different scaling techniques, it is pertinent to ensure that each research instrument employed be adequately tested for reliability and validity. In this study, the researcher ensured that the measure for reliability included an adequate and effective representative set of items that tap the concept. Serious effort was made to ensure that the scale items represented the domain or universe of the concept being measured. In other words, the measurement is a function of how well the dimensions and indicators of the various concepts are been delineated, which logically reflected the study variables. The validation of the instrument would be ensured through my supervisors vetting. Through this process, errors in the questionnaire such as ambiguity, contradictory questions, poor wording of questions, misleading or poor instructions among others would be detected and eliminated.

Tests of Reliability of Instrument

Reliability is the ability of a measuring instrument to achieve consistent results each time it is adopted. However, Nunnally (1979) asserts that the reliability alpha values in determining the internal consistency of the instrument should maintain a minimum threshold of 0.7. Based on this, the Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient method was utilized in this study since it is the most predominant method of testing reliability in social sciences research (Hair, Black, Babin & Anderson 2010).

The Emergent of Social Work in Nigeria

Historically, social work in Nigeria predates colonialism. Kinship system in the traditional Nigerian society provided for family welfare, child welfare, health, mental health, care for the aged, informal education, social planning and development. Extended family met social welfare needs and dealt with problematic behaviours that the community regarded as deviant. However, a well-packaged, formal social work as a profession with well-articulated theories began with colonization in Nigeria (Anucha,

2008). Lagos had for long been in the fore-front of the development of social work in Nigeria significantly during World War II returnees and its attendant social welfare-related problems. Social work is the professional activity of helping individuals, groups and communities enhance or restore their capacity for social functioning. Social workers help people deal with their relationships with others to:

- (a) solve their personal, family and community problems; and
- (b) grow and develop by learning to cope with or shape the social and environmental forces affecting daily life.

Therefore, social work is a profession for those with a spark of idealism, a belief in social justice, and a natural love of working with people. Social work offers the chance to work with and for people of all kinds: rich or poor, young or old, in hospitals, at home, or at work. Social workers render services to the children, families, elderly, persons with disabilities, persons with needs of health and mental health care, youth, delinquents and schools. Social work practice is speedily moving away from residual perspective where an ad hoc or REACTIVE approach was prominent, an approach focusing on problems and gaps – social welfare services were supplied to persons with acute problems as obtained in community of old using community resources; to an institutional perspective where social welfare services are routinely put in place and supplied to meet people's needs as a normal part of life. Institutional perspective in social work believes that it is not people's fault that they require such social services but rather an expected part of the human condition and rights. This institutional perspective is being threatened by developmental perspective in social work, a new concept, which focuses on identification of social interventions that have a positive impact on economic development only (Kirst-Ashman, 2003). This developmental perspective does not take into cognizance the core values of social work which have concern for the worth and dignity of every individual in which ever situation. But developmental perspective focuses only on the economic gain from every social work activity. All social workers must be prepared to tackle this new trend called developmental perspective in an emerging megacity as this will become an issue sooner than later.

Social Work as a Profession

Abraham Flexner in a 1915 lecture, "Is Social Work a Profession?". (Flexner, 2018) delivered at the National Conference on Charities and Corrections, examined the characteristics of a profession with reference to social work. It is not a 'single model', such as that of health, followed by medical professions such as nurses and doctors, but an integrated profession, and the likeness with medical profession is that social work requires a continued study for professional development to retain knowledge and skills that are evidence-based by practice standards. A social work professional's services lead toward the aim of providing beneficial services to individuals, dyads, families, groups, organizations and communities to

achieve optimum psychosocial functioning. (Ontario College 2011). Its seven core functions are described by Popple and Leighninger as:

1. Engagement — the social worker must first engage the client in early meetings to promote a collaborative relationship.
2. Assessment — data must be gathered that will guide and direct a plan of action to help the client.
3. Planning — negotiate and formulate an action plan
4. Implementation — promote resource acquisition and enhance role performance
- Monitoring/Evaluation — on-going documentation through short-term goal attainment of extent to which client is following through
5. Supportive Counseling — affirming, challenging, encouraging, informing, and exploring options
6. Graduated Disengagement — seeking to replace the social worker with a naturally occurring resource. (Popple&Leighninger, 2011)

Six other core values identified by the National Association of Social Workers' (NASW 2002) Code of Ethics are:

1. Service — help people in need and address social problems
2. Social Justice — challenge social injustices
3. Dignity and worth of the person
4. Importance of human relationships
5. Integrity — behave in a trustworthy manner
6. Competence — practice within the areas of one's areas of expertise and develop and enhance professional skill

A historic and defining feature of social work is the profession's focus on individual well-being in a social context and the well-being of society, (Crisp 2012). Social workers promote social justice and social change with and on behalf of clients, (Stefaroi 2014). A "client" can be an individual, family, group, organization, or community, (NASW 2002). In the broadening scope of the modern social worker's role, some practitioners have in recent years traveled to war-torn countries to provide psychosocial assistance to families and survivors, (Keough 2004). Newer areas of social work practice involve management science.(Murali 2014) The growth of "social work administration" for transforming social policies into services and directing activities of an organization toward achievement of goals is a related field.(Rex 1995) Helping clients with accessing benefits such as unemployment insurance and disability benefits, to assist individuals and families in building savings and acquiring assets to improve their financial security over the long-term, to manage large operations, etc. requires social workers to know financial management skills to help clients and organisation's to be financially self-sufficient.(Despard 2010) Financial social work also helps clients with low-income or low to middle-income, people who are either unbanked (do not have a banking account) or underbanked (individuals who have a bank account but tend to rely on high cost non-bank providers for their financial transactions), with better mediation with

financial institutions and induction of money management skills.(Barr, 2004) Another area that social workers are focusing is risk management, risk in social work is taken as Knight in 1921 defined "If you don't even know for sure what will happen, but you know the odds, that is risk and If you don't even know the odds, that is uncertainty." Risk management in social work means minimizing the risks while increasing potential benefits for clients by analyzing the risks and benefits in duty of care or in decisions. (Phyllida, 2001). In the United States, according to the Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration (SAMHSA), a branch of the U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, professional social workers are the largest group of mental health services providers. There are more clinically trained social workers—over 200,000—than psychiatrists, psychologists, and psychiatric nurses combined. Federal law and the National Institutes of Health recognize social work as one of five core mental health professions. (NASW 2013). Examples of fields a social worker may be employed in are poverty relief, life skills education, community development, rural development, forensics and corrections, legislation, industrial relations, project management, child protection, elder protection, women's rights, human rights, systems optimization, finance, addictions rehabilitation, child development, cross-cultural mediation, occupational safety and health, disaster management, mental health, psychosocial therapy, disabilities, etc.

Data Presentation, Analysis and Discussion Of Findings

Presentation of Data

Table 1 Age Distribution of Respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
25-39	146	71.2	71.2	71.2
40-54	39	19.0	19.0	90.2
Valid 55 and above	20	9.8	9.8	100.0
Total	205	100.0	100.0	

Source: Research Survey Data, 2019

Figure 1: bar chart showing age distribution of respondents

From the data in table 1, it can be observed that 5 representing 2.4 percent of the respondents fall within the less than 25 years age bracket. Also, 141 respondents representing 68.8 percent fall within the 25-39 years age bracket. Furthermore, 39 of the respondents representing 19 percent were observed to be between 40-54 years while 20 respondents representing 9.8 percent were between 55 and above age bracket.

Analysis of Research Questions

Research Question:

What is the level of the staff knowledge on the roles of social works professionals in medical field?

Table 2: Response Rates on the level of the staff knowledge on the roles of social works professionals in medical field

	Staff knowledge on the roles of social works professionals	SA	A	U	D	SD	Mean	Std.
1	Social workers are professionally trained to fit into the medical setting	87	83	5	17	13	4.0439	1.16443
2	Social workers play a great role in the well-being of patients in the hospital	29	15	10	101	50	2.38	1.31372
3	Social workers provide social, psychological and financial support to patient in the hospital	31	32	32	67	75	2.09	1.06006
4	Social workers provide psycho-social therapy to patients in the hospital	22	28	14	97	44	2.31	1.21195
5	Social workers acts as mediators between the	27	16	8	102	52	2.49	1.29814

staffs and the patients								
-------------------------	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

Source: Research Survey Data, 2019

The results of table 2 reveals that all items (1-5) expect item one have mean scores below 2.50. The statement ‘Social workers provide social, psychological and financial support to patient in the hospital’ has the lowest mean score (M=2.09; SD=1.06006) followed by ‘Social workers provide psycho-social therapy to patients in the hospital’ (M=2.31; SD= 1.21195), ‘Social workers play a great role in the well-being of patients in the hospital’ (M=2.38;SD=1.31372), ‘Social workers acts as mediators between the staffs and the patients.’ (M=2.49;SD=1.29814), the first statement ‘Social workers are professionally trained to fit into the medical setting’ has the highest mean score of (M=4.0439;SD=1.16443). These shows all the items indicate that most the medical staffs are not aware of the role of social workers at the hospital. This is true since the mean values are below the benchmark of 2.5, meaning that most of the respondents were on the disagree range of the scale, but item one which has the highest mean score shows an indication that the staffs are aware that social workers are part of the medical team but do not know the roles they play in the well-being of patients in the hospital. Thus it is clear that medical staffs are not aware that social workers supports patients financially, provide psycho-social therapy to patients, and also acts as a mediator between the patient and staff hence, their services are underutilized in the hospital.

Summary and Conclusion

Data was analyzed and results presented. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation. The findings revealed that the major factors affecting the integration of social workers in the medical institution are lack of awareness among medical staff. It was revealed through the study that majority of the staffs (82.9%) are aware of the presences of social workers in the hospital, but only 21.4% of them are aware of the roles and cases handled by social workers in the hospital. Other challenges revealed in the study include lack of resources and facilities to handle cases that require social work intervention, too many workloads and less time for social workers in the hospital. The researcher also discovered in the course of the study that there are many cases in the hospital that requires social work attention but few of them are employed to handle these cases. 71.7% of the medical staffs agree that social work unit is understaffed. The major challenges identified in the study involve lack of awareness of the hospital social workers roles among medical staff and knowledge of cases which require social work interventions. The study findings have indicated that only 21.4% of the medical staff knew the roles of hospital social workers. This result shows that roles of social workers are not known by most hospital medical staff, which directly leads to underutilization of hospital social workers as shown in the conceptual framework.

Recommendations

- i. The Government should employ more hospital social workers so that they can be able to meet the demand of their services to patients and clients at the hospital.
- ii. Social workers should be made known to all hospital staff and their roles should be well communicated.

References

Reference

- Ankrah, E. M. (2001). "Social Work Uganda: Survival in the Midst of Turbulence," in Hokenstad, M.; Khinduka, S. & Midgley, J. Profiles in International Social Work, Washington, DC: NASW Press.
- Anucha, U., (2008). Exploring a New Direction for Social Work Education and Training in Nigeria. *Social Work Education*. 27. 229-242. 10.1080/02615470701381459.
- Babbie, E. (2007) *The practice of social research*. 11th Edition, Thompson Wadsworth, Belmont.
- Bar-On, A. A. (2004). "The Elusive Boundaries of Social Work," *Journal of Sociology and Social Welfare*, 21(3), 53-67.
- Barker, M. (2013), Anaesthetic emergencies. *Veterinary Nursing Journal*, 28: 220-224. doi:10.1111/vnj.12047
- Barr, M. S. (2004). *Banking the poor: Policies to bring low-income Americans into the financial mainstream*. Washington, D.C.: Brookings Institution.
- Blyton, P. & Turnbull, P. (1992), 'HRM: Debates, Dilemmas and Contradictions', in P. Blyton & P. Turnbull (eds), *Reassessing Human Resource Management*, London: Sage, Publications Inc.
- Birkenmaier, J., & Curley, J., (2009). "Financial credit: Social work's role in empowering low-income families". *Journal of Community Practice*. 17(3):251–268.
- Braun, V., and Clarke, V. (2006). *Using the thematic analysis in psychology*. Qualitative research in psychology, 3(2), 77-101. London: Routledge.
- Breakwell, G. M. & Rowell, C. (2002). *Social Work: The Social Psychological Approach*, Berkshire: Van Nostrand Reinhold Co.
- Breakwell, G. M. & Rowell, C. (2002). *Social Work: The Social Psychological Approach*, Berkshire: Van Nostrand Reinhold Co.

Breakwell, G. M., & Rowett, C. (1982). *Social Work: The Social Psychological Approach*. Wokingham, U. K.: Van Nostrand Reinhold.

Canadian Association of Social Workers "What is Social Work?" www.casw-acts.ca. Retrieved May 13, 2019.

Canadian Association of Social Workers "What is Social Work?" www.casw-acts.ca. Retrieved July 17, 2019.

Canadian Association of Social Workers "What is Social Work?" www.casw-acts.ca. Retrieved July 19, 2019.

Child, J. (1969). *British Management Thought: A Critical Analysis*, London: George Allen & Unwin.

[Charity Organization Societies: 1877-1893 - Social Welfare History Project](#)". *Social Welfare History Project*. February 4, 2013. Retrieved December 29, 2017.

Crisp, B.R., & Beddoe, L., (2012). *Promoting Health and Well-being in Social Work Education*. Routledge.

Despard, M., & Chowa, G.A.N., (2010). "Social workers' interest in building individuals' financial capabilities". *Journal of Financial Therapy*. 1 (1): 23–41.

Digestive Program". *Current Problems in Pediatric and Adolescent Health Care*. 48 (4): 111–112.

[Dorrien, G., \(2011\). "Fostering Democratic Citizenship: Jane Addams". *Social Ethics in the Making: Interpreting an American Tradition*. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons. p. 168. ISBN 9781444393798](#). Retrieved May 13, 2019.

Dunlop, J. T. (1958) *Industrial Relations Systems*. New York: Holt Rinehart and Winston
Fajana, S. (2000) *Industrial Relations in Nigeria: Theory and Features* (2nd Ed.). Lagos: Labofin publishers

Eysenck, H. J. Charles C. T., (1967). *The biological basis of personality*. Springfield, IL:

Ferdinand Tönnies (ed. Jose Harris), *Community and Civil Society*, Cambridge University Press (2001), hardcover, 266 pages, ISBN 0-521-56119-1; trade paperback, Cambridge University Press (2001), 266 pages, ISBN 0-521-56782-3

Flexner, A., (2018). "Is social work a profession?". New York, The New York school of philanthropy – via Internet Archive.

Fonash, A., (2018). "The Role of the Medical Social Worker in a Pediatric Aero-

[Francis J. T., \(2005\). *Encyclopedia of Canadian Social Work*. Wilfrid Laurier Univ. Press. pp. 219, 236. ISBN 978-0-88920-436-2](#).

- Mayo, E. (1933). *The Human Problems of Industrial Civilization*, New York: Macmillan Company.
- Morris, P. (2008). Reinterpreting Abraham Flexner's Speech, "Is Social Work a Profession?": Its Meaning and Influence on the Field's Early Professional Development. *Social Service Review*, 82(1), 29-60. doi:10.1086/529399
- Murali D. N; Erick G. G., (2014). *Evidence Based Macro Practice in Social Work*. Gregory Publishing Company. ISBN 978-0-911541-94-6.
- Midgley, J. (1981). *Professional Imperialism: Social work the Third World*, London: Heinemann.
- Nachimias, J. (2003). *Research methodology in the Social Science*.(5th Ed): London: St. Mart Press Inc.
- .
- Nair, U., Yen, W. L., Mari, M., Cao, Y., Xie, Z., Baba, M., ...Klionsky, D. J. (2012). A role for Atg8-PE deconjugation in autophagosome biogenesis. *Autophagy*, 8(5), 780–793. doi:10.4161/auto.19385
- National Association of Social Workers "Code of Ethics (English and Spanish)" socialworkers.org. Archived from the original on June 6, 2002.
- National Association of Social Workers (NASW), www.naswdc.org. Archived from [the original](#) on May 31, 2002. Retrieved July 19, 2019.
- "National Association of Social Workers".NASW.Retrieved September 6, 2019.
- Nunnally, J. C. (1978). *Psychometric theory* (2nd ed.). New York: McGraw-Hill "Ontario College of Social Workers and Social Service Workers: The Centre for Education & Training" (PDF). 2011. Retrieved November 8, 2019
- PhyllidaParsole. *Risk assessment in social care and social work*. 2001. Jessica Kingsley Publishers.
- Pople, P. R. and Leighninger, L.,(2011) *Social Work, Social Welfare*, American Society. Boston: Allyn& Bacon
- Pavesi. M, Devlin N., Hakimi Z., Nazir J., Herdman M., Hoyle C.&Odeyemi I. A. (2013) Understanding the effects on HR-QoL of treatment for overactive bladder: a detailed analysis of EQ-5D clinical trial data for mirabegron, *Journal of Medical Economics*, 16:7, 866-876, DOI: 10.3111/13696998.2013.802240
- Reyna VF, Farley F (2006) Risk and Rationality in Adolescent Decision Making: Implications for Theory, Practice, and Public Policy. *Administrative Affairs and Employment*, (1995).Law and employment regulations. Tehran: Administrative Affairs

and Employment organization publication. *Journal of Social Science for Policy Implications*, 2(2), 59 – 68.

Rex A. S., (1995). *Social Work Administration: Dynamic Management and Human Relationships*. Allyn and Bacon. pp. 2–3. ISBN 978-0-13-669037-5.

Romich, J.; Simmelink, J.; Holt, S. D., (2007). "When working harder does not pay: Low-income working families, tax liabilities, and benefit reductions" (PDF). *Families in Society*. 88 (3): 418–426. doi:10.1606/1044-3894.3651.

Rwomile, A. and Ratithokwa, L. (2006). *Social work Africa: Issues and challenges*. *Journal of Social Development in Africa* (1996), 11(2), 5-19.

Samadi Rad, Anvar. (2008). *social work in Iran*. Kayhan. *Journal of Social Science for Policy Implications*, 2(2), 59 - 68

Standards for Clinical Social Work Practice (2005). Retrieved on 16th November, 2016 from: https://www.socialworkers.org/practice/NASWClinicalSWS_tandards.pdf

Sherraden, M.; Laux, S. & Kaufman, C., (2007). "Financial education for social workers" *.Journal of Community Practice*. 15 (3): 9–36. doi:10.1300/J125v15n03_02.

[Social Work Profession](#). *Encyclopedia of Social Work*. 20. Summer 2017

NASW, Code of Ethics

Stefaroi, P., (2014). *Humane & Spiritual Qualities of the Professional in Humanistic Social Work: Humanistic Social Work – The Third Way in Theory and Practice*. Charleston: Createspace.

Stone, R. (1995). *Human Resource Management*, (2nd Edition)., Milton: Wiley & Son.

Taylor, F. (1974). *Scientific Management*, New York: Harper & Row.

Thackeray, M. G., Farley, O. W., & Skidmore, R. A. (1994). *Introduction to Social Work*, New Jersey: Prentice-Hall, Englewood Cliffs.

Tonnies, F. (1887). *Fundamental Concept of Sociology*, New York: Oxford University Press.

Wilson, K., Ruch, G., Lymbery, M., & Cooper, A. (2008). *Social Work*. Harlow, UK, Longman, Pearson NASW Press.

Wodarski, J. S., Feit, M. D., (2012). "Social Group Work Practice: An Evidence- Based Approach". *Journal of Evidence-Based Social Work*. 9 (4): 414–420. doi:10.1080/15433714.2012.695719. ISSN 1543-3714.

["1800s"](#). *Family Action: About Us*. Archived from [the original](#) on July 18, 2011. Retrieved November 17, 2018.

Samadi, R. (2008) Stellar structure and evolution (488),(2), pp705 – 714

Steve, M., (2011.),", Asian Economic and Social Society, 1(5), 181-187.

William, M.M., Daniel, R. Z., Stephen M.J., Searle, E., 2014, Nucleic Acids Research, Volume 42, Issue D1, 1 January 2014, Pages D749–D755,

Yin, R. K. (1994).Discovering the Future of the Case Study.Method in Evaluation Research. *Evaluation Practice*, 15(3), 283–290.